

A method to rank global DEMs quality focused on their horizontal accuracy

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Abstract— Currently there are various global digital elevation models (GDEM) and it would be necessary to have measures that help decide which one to use according to the derived product that we need. The DEMIX Project addresses this problem. In this communication we show an automatic measure that assesses the planimetric quality of a DEM product (DEM) and that allows ordering from highest to lowest, according to planimetric quality, any DEM and particularly a set of GDEMs. The planimetric quality of a DEM is assessed by comparing its contours with their homologous ones belonging to a reference DEM (DEMref) of greater accuracy. The area enclosed by homologous contours is an indicator of DEM's accuracy: the smaller the area enclosed by homologous contours, the greater horizontal accuracy. In this study, the area divided by the average length of the contours is used to estimate the DEM horizontal accuracy compared with a DEMref. One of the great advantages of this method is that it is completely automatic (we do not need to identify the homologous curves). Although the method can be used to compare any DEM, in this study we have used 2 GDEMs (ASTER and NASADEM) as DEM which have 30 m of spatial resolution and the DEMref is the Spanish MDT05 (5 m of spatial resolution) generated by the Spanish Instituto Geográfico Nacional (IGN).

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital elevation models (DEM) are used in many branches of knowledge, such as Civil Engineering, Environment, Natural Risk Management, Climate Change, etc. Many products are derived from them, such as slope maps, orientations, basins and hydrographic networks, optimal locations for mobile phone antennas, etc. Due to the large number of DEMs applications, numerous studies of their quality have also been carried out, as shown in [1-3]. In most cases, the DEM vertical accuracy is studied [2, 4] and planimetric accuracy is left aside as it is more

difficult to compute because the difficulty of identifying homologous points between the DEM and the DEMref or reference control elements [4]. In the DEM vertical accuracy studies, the height values of a sample of points obtained from a DEMref or directly in the field using, for example, GNSS, are compared with their homologous ones in the DEM whose accuracy is to be computed; these studies often use classical statistics (RMSE, μ , σ , MAE, NMAD, etc.) [5, 6]. The mentioned above homologous points are selected from the DEM at the same horizontal coordinates that the ground truth points had, but how do we know that these homologous points are really the same in both datasets? Proceeding in this way, we are considering that DEM has no planimetric error with respect to the ground truth. There are so few studies of planimetric accuracy in DEMs because of the difficulty of identifying homologous points in DEM and DEMref. Some early proposals for planimetric accuracy evaluation measures appear in [7] but do not allow for automation of the process, which makes implementation difficult. And more recently, measures that evaluate the planimetric accuracy of a DEM have been proposed [8-11]; Among them, perhaps the best is the one based on the area enclosed by homologous contours that intersect, considering as homologous those contours that represent the same altitude in the DEM and the DEMref respectively [8, 9]; this method solves the problem of identifying homologous elements in both the DEMref and DEM, since if no altitudinal bias exists, the homologous contours represent the same planimetric space of the terrain, and the non-coincident part expresses the planimetric discrepancy between the DEM and the DEMref.

In the present communication we develop an application example of the horizontal accuracy method based on contours

[9], which could be used to rank GDEMs produced by different sources from best to worst.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

A. Material

In order to illustrate the method, 2 DEM of 10 km x 10 km located in Sierra Nevada, Granada, (Spain) have been used. The source GDEMs are ASTER V003 and NASADEM. Both are open data that we have downloaded from the NASA website <https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/search>. ASTER and NASADEM have a cell size of 1 arcsecond which is roughly equivalent to 30 m. The DEMref selected was the MDT05 produced by the IGN of Spain, whose cell size is 5 m.

Figure 1: GDEM samples geolocation at Granada (Southern Spain)

The coordinate reference system (CRS) for ASTER and NASADEM was WGS84 while that of MDT05 was ETRS89 UTM zone 30N. To give the DEM samples (MDT05, NASADEM and ASTER) the same limits and the same cell size, an alignment was carried out, taking MDT05 as a reference and resampling to the nearest neighbor. Finally, the 3 samples were stored in the CRS ETRS89 UTM zone 30N and their respective contours were derived. The contour step had a value of 125 m, beginning the first contour at an altitude of 950 m and ending the last contour at 2825 m height.

B. Methodology

The DEM horizontal accuracy with respect to DEMref is estimated as a function of the area enclosed by homologous contour lines. In Fig.2 we can see 2 types of homologous contours: suppose that the contours labeled as A belong to DEMref and those labeled as B belong to DEM; the contours are not coincident because DEM lacks accuracy with respect to DEMref and the inaccuracy magnitude is intuited by the amount of enclosed surface (grey color) between homologous contours.

Figure 2: Area between overlapping contours (A and B)

The inaccuracy magnitude of the (H_{acc}) for a single contour in DEM could be estimated by the equation (1) where L_A and L_B are the lengths of the contours in DEM and DEMref respectively and $Area$ is the area enclosed by both contours.

$$H_{acc} = \frac{Area}{(L_A + L_B)/2} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

An alternative could be to use the L_B as denominator, and it would deserve a comparison with our proposal.

In a DEMref, at a particular altitude (h_i) there will be a number of contours m whose total length will be $refLT_i$; in a DEM for the same h_i , there will be a number of curves n whose total length will be $proLT_i$, and the total area enclosed by the homologous contours of DEMref and DEM at altitude h_i will be $AreaT_i$. If we only consider the altitude h_i to compute H_{acc} , then $H_{acc} = AreaT_i / (refLT_i + proLT_i) / 2$. Since the number of altitudes for which the contour are calculated is variable $i=1, 2, \dots, k$, the estimate of the total horizontal accuracy (HT_{acc}) of DEM with respect to DEMref will be as shown in equation (2):

$$HT_{acc} = \frac{\sum_i^k AreaT_i}{\sum_i^k (refLT_i + proLT_i) / 2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

It is difficult to automate the HT_{acc} computation because the correspondence between homologous contours is not a bijective map; a priori the correspondence could have any setting, e.g. 1->1, 0->1, 1->n, n->1 and in general manner m->n. To understand all the cases that could happen you can consult [9].

The greatest difficulty to automate the process is to prove the following theorem:

The number of possible different Regions in a DEM ($REG^k_{x_s}$) is exactly 2 and they are complementary.

The regions to which the theorem refers are those that appear in gray in the images f and i respectively of Fig. 3. The correct region will be the one with the smallest surface (image f in Fig.

3). The images a and b in Fig. 3 represent DEMref and DEM respectively, assuming that all contour have the same height. As shown in Fig. 2, the correspondence between homologous contours is not bijective. The images f and i are the 2 complementary regions mentioned in the theorem; f is derived applying the mathematical operation symmetric difference between the d and e images. Similarly is derived the i image.

Figure 3: Theorem illustration. Images a and b show homologous contours with no bijective correspondence, and images f an i show the only two possible regions after applying method explained in [9]

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The algorithm presented in [9] has been applied using MDT05 as a reference and the graphic result is shown in Fig. 4. The images that allow HT_{acc} to be computed are those labeled with NASA vs MDT05 and ASTER vs MDT05. Fig. 4 includes an additional result (ASTER vs NASADEM) that does not measure the horizontal accuracy of the DEM but shows the horizontal discrepancy between ASTER and NASADEM comparing their homologous contours.

In order to have a better understanding of how the algorithm works, in Fig. 4 two examples of each of the three results have been enlarged. These examples have been framed in red and green, giving rise to the left column (red) and the left column (green) respectively. In both examples the area between contour lines of ASTER vs MDT05 is greater than the area NASA vs MDT05, so it is expected that the best value of HT_{acc} belongs to NASADEM.

The HT_{acc} numerical values for ASTER and NASADEM are shown in Table 1, although before performing the HT_{acc} final

computation, the horizontal accuracy (H_{acci}) for each curve elevation (h_i) has been computed: each row corresponds to the values of contours mean length ($(refLT_i + proLT_i)/2$), area between homologous contours (A_{refT_i}) and DEM horizontal accuracy o_i if only h_i (H_{acci}) is considered. It is observed that for all the h_i values the H_{acci} measure is very similar except for the value $h_i = 950$ m where the horizontal accuracy values are much greater than in the rest. This is because there is a relationship between homologous contours of $1 \rightarrow 0$, i.e., both in ASTER and in NASADEM there is a contour that does not appear in MDT05, which produces a very large area (marked with a blue ellipse in Fig. 4).

In this example where we compute the HT_{acc} for ASTER and NASADEM, the best global accuracy is obtained by NASADEM, which has $HT_{acc} = 10.7$ m compared to ASTER's $HT_{acc} = 14.0$ m, which implies that NASADEM improves ASTER's horizontal accuracy by 23%.

I. CONCLUSIONS

In this communication we have presented a method that allows ranking a series of GDEMs produced by different sources; the method is based on a measure that can estimate the horizontal accuracy (HT_{acc}). To perform the method requires a DEMref that will be the ground truth to compare the DEM (GDEMs) with. Furthermore, HT_{acc} has the advantage that it can be automated according to the algorithm [9]. We consider that this measure is of interest to the DEMIX project, which aims to compare different GDEMs in order to rank them. A remarkable property from the method is that it can identify homologous elements in DEMs (contours). This ability is hard to find in other methods, even those based on manual processes since there is usually no certainty about which pair of points are homologous in DEMref and DEM.

Finally, the graphic representation capabilities of one of the measurement components (area between homologous contours) demonstrates in which areas the greatest DEM inaccuracies happen (Fig. 4).

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS (HEADING 1)

This research has been partially funded by the Project: "Functional Quality of Digital Elevation Models in Engineering" of the State Research Agency with code PID2019-106195RB-I00/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, more information at https://coello.ujaen.es/investigacion/web_giic/funquality4dem/.

Figure 4: Area inside homologous contours after comparing DEMref and DEM

Table 1: Horizontal Accuracy estimation for ASTER and NASADEM

h_i Contour height (m)	ASTER vs MDT05			NASA vs MDT05		
	$(refLT_i + proLT_i)/2$ (m)	$AreaT_i$ (m ²)	H_{acc}^i (m)	$(refLT_i + proLT_i)/2$ (m)	$AreaT_i$ (m ²)	H_{acc}^i (m)
950	2371,0	276131,3	116,5	1902,2	268245,4	141,0
1075	20908,0	259411,0	12,4	20054,9	227050,7	11,3
1200	31726,1	405635,7	12,8	31429,9	336515,7	10,7
1325	37552,4	465815,1	12,4	36922,7	414114,5	11,2
1450	51316,5	746549,1	14,5	49595,4	554530,1	11,2
1575	46881,6	653031,8	13,9	46079,8	443547,1	9,6

1700	47503,2	675658,8	14,2	46984,4	516096,0	11,0
1825	41267,9	543688,1	13,2	40544,6	389059,7	9,6
1950	32380,7	409800,2	12,7	32211,5	286557,0	8,9
2075	27934,4	358605,1	12,8	27393,5	241606,8	8,8
2200	24431,5	319213,5	13,1	24350,4	223654,3	9,2
2325	19709,6	253086,0	12,8	18886,1	170584,4	9,0
2450	7929,7	100859,4	12,7	7779,4	55654,7	7,2
2575	3619,2	54334,8	15,0	3570,4	29773,6	8,3
2700	2059,8	30973,8	15,0	2023,6	19112,4	9,4
2825	633,4	8220,8	13,0	655,3	5805,7	8,9
		HT_{acc}	14,0		HT_{acc}	10,7

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